

AN EYE FOR AN EYE INFECTION: VISION AND AWARENESS FOR OPHTHALMIC COMPLICATIONS DUE TO DENTAL PROCEDURES - A SHORT REVIEW

***Dr. Runal Bansod¹, Dr. Swapnil Gotekar², Dr. Lajri Bagde¹, Dr. Vidyarjan Sukhdeve³,
Dr. Isha Madne¹**

1. Assistant Professor, Department of Oral Medicine & Radiology,
SDKS Dental College & Hospital, Nagpur
2. Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology,
Government Medical College & Hospital, Bhandara
3. Assistant Professor, Department of Oral Medicine & Radiology,
Yogita Dental College & Hospital, Khed

***Dr. Runal Bansod**

Corresponding author

Abstract: The association between dental health and visionary health is quite uncommon, but certain cases have thrown a light on the fact that the association between the two is not something to be ignored completely. As it might lead to severe ophthalmic complications. Studies have shown that dental infections or inflammation can lead to temporary blurry vision and carelessness while doing rotary dental procedures might harm the eye. Hence, proper eye protective measures are required to safeguard the eyes from harmful aerosols released during rotary dental procedures. This review throws a light on the same.

Keywords: dental, eye, vision, ophthalmic, aerosols.

Introduction & Background

The relationship between infected teeth and diseases of the eye has been known for a while. Several centuries ago, a case of ophthalmia and loss of eye due to an abscessed tooth had been reported. In 1795, the connection between dental irritation and diseases of the eye has been described, and in 1817, a case was reported in which contraction of the visual field was carried out away with by the extraction of carious tooth. Many cases of defective vision were treated effectually by the removal of underlying pathological conditions discovered in the mouth.¹

Dental treatment procedures can cause ocular injuries due to microbial, physical or chemical factors. Hence, both the dentist and patient are at a risk for developing eye infections or injuries due to the constant use of power-driven handpieces which generate aerosols. Operative procedures like removal of dental caries make use dental handpieces on a frequent basis which release a lot of aerosols into the atmosphere. The most common cause for eyelid swelling was microbial infection present in the carious lesion which was transmitted via the aerosols generated by the airtor during the cavity cutting procedure.^{2,3,4} In surveys conducted by Ramos MF⁵ & Stokes AN⁶, it is emphasized that the awareness and eye protection for the dental staff is not up to the standards. Ocular complications such as defective vision, ophthalmia, orbital cellulitis, and blindness (temporary or permanent) are rare complications due to dental infection.

Particulate matter is mostly lodged in the cornea or conjunctival sac which causes redness & irritation to the eye. In serious eye injuries like perforation, irritation of lens might occur due to penetration of the particle into deeper tissues.^{7,8} Since eyes are very delicate structures, hence they easily get affected with infectious things like aerosols without any contact. And once contacted, the infection can range from a mild to severe swelling to serious complications

like retinal damage, or formation of scars and ulcers which can cause obstruction of vision.⁹

In a study done by B.A. Aydil et al.¹⁰, it was demonstrated that ocular injuries reported were significantly higher among the participants without any eye protection and also suggested that there were major inadequacies in protocols for the eye/face protection.

Plenty of evidence in case histories is present which quotes the direct relation of foci of infection of mouth to inflammatory disturbances of the eye. Hence it is of utmost importance to spread awareness regarding the same amongst all the eye surgeons and oral health care professionals to clearly investigate and act accordingly. Past 15-20 years, the topic of dental focal infection has received a lot of attention due to the experimental work of various researchers. But currently, there are no specific guidelines in preventing and managing ocular problems.

With the advanced knowledge about infection control and personal protection, a lot of emphasis is required on eye protection protocols. Frequently performed restorative and operative procedures like caries excavation, restorations, oral prophylaxis, etc. are performed using high power-driven handpieces. A lot of particulate matter like spicules of caries, calculus, amalgam, blood etc may get released which may get lodged into tissues during various dental procedures. The working rotary handpiece generates a lot of aerosols which may carry an array of microorganisms producing infections to respiratory tract, eyes, skin, etc. Eye infections can occur due to a variety of organisms such as bacterial, viral, fungal and helminths and its severity can range from mild swelling of the eyelid to complete blindness of the eyes. Hence, dentistry is one of the professions which is highly risked for ocular infections on a routine basis.

Tremendous effort has to be created between the medical and dental professionals to understand the need for eye care. Hence, certain national safety agencies, like Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), American National Standard Institute (ANSI), American Dental Association (ADA) have set prompt guidelines for the proper usage of infection control measures and personal protective equipment (PPE).¹¹

Review of case report

In a case report reported by Arvind R et al³, A 22-year-old female dentist had treated a patient, with deep caries management under rubber dam isolation. During the treatment, the dentist got injured with a spicule from the cavity in the right eye. She rinsed her eyes with the water couple of times. In spite of regularly rinsing, the dentist developed irritation and foreign body sensation in the right eye immediately after the procedure. Three days later, a full-blown infection was noticed. She developed redness, pain, in ability to fully open the eye without discomfort, yellowish discharge which often sealed the eye shut during sleeping, and generalized malaise. The right eye had diffuse swelling of the upper lid with a normal anterior segment and mild pain and difficulty in opening (Fig. 1). Mild congestion was seen in the left eye (Fig. 1) and then she visited the Ophthalmology department. Upon consultation, the ophthalmologist performed slit lamp examination and was diagnosed with Bacterial Blepharitis. There was no blurring of vision, no dilation of pupils, and no abnormality was detected in the adjoining structures. She was prescribed antibiotic ointment (Moxigram, Moxifloxacin Hydrochloride 0.5% w/v three times a day for a week) with topical eye drops (Toba, Tobramycin Ophthalmic solution, 0.3% w/v four times a day for 1 week) and normal lubricating eye drops (Zyaqua, Carboxymethyl cellulose sodium eye drops, 0.5% w/v) for one month for symptomatic relief. Along with this, she was advised to apply warm

compresses to the eyelids for several minutes, two to four times daily. She was counselled to take complete rest, to avoid any cosmetics and not to treat any patients till the symptoms resolve. After 4 days of the treatment, the eyelid swelling got resolved and there was no pain and redness. After a week, she treated another patient for direct pulp capping procedure and encountered similar infection again, but the severity of the infection was in a milder form. The right eye showed nodular swelling at the medial margin of the upper lid with normal anterior segment (Fig. 2). There was no associated redness or pain present. The patient was advised to continue the lubricating eye drops. She was informed to report back to the ophthalmologist if the symptoms persist. After a month of treatment, she had no redness, no eyelid swelling or pain and had complete recovery.

Fig 1- View of eye showing diffuse swelling of the upper lid of the right eye with a normal anterior segment and mild congestion in the left eye, 3 days after performing the dental procedure.¹¹

Fig 2- View of the eye showing nodular swelling at the medial margin of the upper lid of the right eye with normal anterior segment after 1 week of performing the dental procedure (Recurrent infection)¹¹

This case report is reviewed in this review as a proof for the association between ocular infections secondary to allergic reaction due to dental treatment among the dentists.

Conclusion

Some associations are rare, but the damage caused by them is something which needs to be aware of. Wearing proper protective eye gears and eye shields is of utmost importance to protect the delicate eyes from undergoing damage or infections.

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